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CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for
case/impact studies for geoengineering

README-3

Pasquale Sellitto¹, Mona Kosary¹, Michaël Hopfner²

¹Laboratoire Interuniversitaire des Systèmes Atmosphériques (LISA), Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL),
Université Paris Est Créteil (UPEC), France

²Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344
EggensteinLeopoldshafen, Germany

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This document will describe the CAIRT L1b test data products for case/impact studies for geoengineering, as well as the auxiliary data needed for the processor. The intent of this document is to be adopted as README for potential L1b users.</p> <p>This draft version of the document has as the main objective to define the structure of the document and to agree on the main content.</p>		
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<i>Names of authors</i> Pasquale Sellitto, Michaël Hopfner		
<i>ESA Technical Officer</i> Alex Hoffmann Division Mission Science Division Directorate Directorate of Earth Observation Programmes	<i>ESA budget heading</i>	

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List of acronyms

CAIRT	Changing-Atmosphere InfraRed Tomography
TDS	Test Data Set
CESM	Community Earth System Model (CESM)
WACCM	Whole Atmosphere Community Climate Model

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This purpose of this document is to provide a description of the test data set (TDS) products that are produced within the context of the CAIRT mission for case/impact studies for geoengineering (WP 7300 and 8300).

The TDS produced for the simulations for CAIRT will be obtained using WACCM simulations described by Tilmes et al. 2020 and available at the following repository: <https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/d651024/>.

1.2 The CESM/WACCM simulations data sets

For this impact study, CESM2/WACCM6 datasets for the Stratospheric Aerosol Geoengineering experiments of Tilmes et al. 2020 are used.

In particular, three experiments have been performed:

- Geo SSP5-34-OS 1.5: based on a baseline obtained with the CMIP6 WACCM6 SSP5-34-OS experiment, stratospheric sulphur injections are simulated, with the aim of limiting the global temperature increase to 1.5°C above 1850–1900 conditions.
- Geo SSP5-34-OS 2.0: Based on a baseline obtained with the CMIP6 WACCM6 SSP5-34-OS experiment, stratospheric sulphur injections are simulated, with the aim of limiting the global temperature increase to 2.0°C above 1850–1900 conditions.
- Geo SSP5-85 1.5: Based on a baseline obtained with the CMIP6 WACCM6 SSP5-85 experiment, stratospheric sulphur injections are simulated, with the aim of limiting the global temperature increase to 1.5°C above 1850–1900 conditions.

For the three experiments, sulphur dioxide injections were applied at four predefined latitudes, 30N, 15N, 15S, and 30S, to reach three surface temperature targets: global mean temperature (mentioned above), and inter-hemispheric and pole-to-equator temperature gradients. This is obtained using a feedback algorithm.

1.3 Input file format

Both monthly and 5-days data sets are used, including the scenario pseudo-reality parameters: vertical profiles of SO₂, liquid H₂SO₄ (within sulphate aerosols) and ozone volume mixing ratios. Please find a detailed description of the fields in these files at the following link: <https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/d651024/>.

1.4 Output file format

The monthly CAIRT synthetic SO₂ and sulphate aerosol output datasets (CAIRT pseudo-observations) over 2034 are provided in NetCDF format at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17384389>.

The simulation corresponds to the Geo SSP5-34-OS 2.0 stratospheric aerosol injection experiment and, in particular, the SAI injection in January 2034, as the pseudo-reality scenario. The files contain SO₂ and liquid H₂SO₄ (within sulphate aerosols) volume mixing ratios, derived from the CESM2(WACCM6) simulations and degraded to the CAIRT resolution with added noise components (systematic and random noise). The data are provided on the intended CAIRT orbit and measurement sampling locations. All variables include descriptive attributes (units, long_name) to ensure consistent interpretation in subsequent analysis and model–observation comparison.

2 Literature

Tilmes, S., MacMartin, D. G., Lenaerts, J. T. M., van Kampenhout, L., Muntjewerf, L., Xia, L., Harrison, C. S., Krumhardt, K. M., Mills, M. J., Kravitz, B., and Robock, A.: Reaching 1.5 and 2.0 °C global surface temperature targets using stratospheric aerosol geoengineering, *Earth Syst. Dynam.*, 11, 579–601, <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-11-579-2020>, 2020.